

Seed viability was monitored for 12 mo. The average germination percentage from two replications is in Figure 2.

Seeds had varying dormancies. Those from shallow water plots generally had poorer viability retention than those from deep water plots (Fig. 2). But, irrespective of variety, germination up to 4 mo. after harvest was slightly higher for seeds from the shallow water plot. Viability of seeds from such fields was highest in Apr, then abruptly decreased.

Seeds from the deep water plot maintained proper viability until Jul, after which viability decreased. They retained

more than 80% germination ability beyond 7 mo. No remarkable varietal difference in germination was recorded for seeds from either water regime.

In shallow water, many seeds of both varieties were underdeveloped, with high grain sterility and low grain filling. This may have been caused by lodging and drought at the grain ripening stage. Abnormal grain formation probably reduced nutrient supply to the grain, which may have reduced seed viability. Drought and lodging normally do not occur at grain filling under deep water conditions.

The viability of rice seeds generally is

controlled by genetic and environmental conditions. Our research emphasizes that, if high seed viability is to be maintained, multiplication of deep water rice seed should be done in native deep water environmental conditions rather than in lowland field conditions. □

1. Duration of crop growth phases and weekly variations in water level of 2 field conditions, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, India.

2. Monthly changes in germination of seeds of 2 floating rice varieties from deep water and normal fields. Chinsurah, India.

Pest control and management DISEASES

Siratro, a new alternate host of *Thanatephorus cucumeris*

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Sheath blight (ShB) of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, imperfect state of *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk, has been a minor disease in Tamil Nadu. In Nov–Dec 1983, however, siratro *Macroptilium atropurpureum*, a fodder crop grown after rice, was completely defoliated. Dark brown sclerotia were

abundant on the dried leaves.

Infected plants were collected to isolate the causal organism. The fungus was identified as *R. solani*. The pathogenicity of the fungus was confirmed by artificial inoculation using mycelial bits from a culture or sclerotia collected from infected leaves of siratro. The first symptoms were 10 × 6 mm greenish grey, ellipsoidal spots on the leaves. Artificial inoculation on rice seedlings produced typical ShB symptoms in 7 d.

We compared the organism isolated from naturally infected rice seedlings

with that from siratro. The morphological characters were similar and the relationship was further confirmed by the two isolates' ability to anastomose.

The isolated organism was cross-inoculated on potted rice seedlings and siratro plants. In 5–7 d, both plants developed symptoms similar to those observed in the fields.

Our information indicates the potential of siratro as source of ShB inoculum. Feeding infected fodder to cattle will also disseminate the pathogen through cow dung. □